

New Aspects for the Use of Fibre-Reinforced Metals for
Electrical Contacts

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Under electrical contact both the touching of two electrically conducting bodies for the purpose of transmitting electrical energy and the component itself which brings this about are understood. Electrical contacts have the function of closing electrical circuits, carrying the current temporarily or for longer periods of time, opening closed circuits again and thus interrupting the current. After a large number of switching cycles, after a long interval between switching, or after carrying current for a long time the contact material should not change the way it functions. In addition, contacts should have as long a lifetime as possible, i.e. the material loss should be as small as possible.

These basic requirements which are placed on electrical contacts imply certain physical, chemical, mechanical, and technological properties. According to the structural design of the contact points used in electrical instruments and systems, the following are differentiated:

- a) Normally-closed contacts where no separation of the contact surfaces which are touching takes place during operation;
- b) Sliding or wipe contacts which permit the motion of one contact surface along a second contact surface without interrupting the electrical current;

- c) Movable contacts which have the function of closing circuits, carrying current temporarily or for a longer period of time, opening closed circuits again and interrupting the current.

Especially the two last-mentioned groups are exposed to many different electrical and mechanical demands. The use of pure metals or alloys does not lead to the desired success in many cases here. Pure metals, especially the most important contact metal silver, are soft and have a strong tendency to weld when switching on overcurrents and to sputter under the influence of arcing. Should the well-conducting silver be made harder, more burnoff-resistant, or less susceptible to welding through alloying, the electrical resistance increases and the melting point decreases in many cases. Accordingly, favorable effects can be obtained by alloying only with the loss of other desired properties. The use of composites-composed of a number of components - which exhibit new kinds of properties offers a way out. If suitable additives are embedded in a matrix of a metal which conducts well, e.g. to improve contact properties, the conductivity usually sinks only in accordance with the volume per cent of the added material. Because of these advantages, composites have already been used in contact technology in many ways for some time.

According to the physical structure of the composites used for electrical contacts, the following are differentiated: particle composites, interpenetrating composites, fiber-reinforced composites, and laminated composites.

Contact technology already used these composites quite early. Already at the turn of the century, copper-graphite-sinter composites were used for electrical contacts.

The improvement of metallurgical processes made possible the manufacture of highly burnoff-resistant AgW, CuW, and AgMo contact materials which could be produced both as particle and as interpenetrating composi-

tes. During the Second World War AgCdO was introduced. This material contains finely dispersed CdO particles in a silver matrix and is still considered a standard material for electrical contacts today. It is distinguished above all by the anti-arcing action of the CdO. In addition to CdO, other metal oxides such as SnO₂, ZnO, Al₂O₃, etc., for example, are embedded in a silver matrix, for example, to reduce the susceptibility to welding when switching on larger currents.

It has been found in many cases that further improvement of the contact properties can be obtained with a fibre-shaped embedment of the second phase in the matrix. The first fibre-reinforced composites were already proposed as contact materials at the start of World War II. The embedment for contact purposes of wires or fibres of a refractory metal in a matrix of a metal which is a good conductor has already been described in American patent literature in 1940 (figure 1). The fibers in these contacts serve to increase the mechanical strength and have the function of reducing the mechanical wear and preventing particles of the contact from breaking off. [1]

Because of the high manufacturing costs the tungsten or molybdenum fibre-reinforced silver or copper materials have not been able to prevail on a large scale to date, although Cu/W, for example, shows some properties interesting for contact purposes. Thus a Cu/W fibre-reinforced composite with a 40 vol.-% proportion of tungsten fibers has in the fiber direction an electrical conductivity about 30 % higher than the corresponding isotropically sintered material.

The main goal of present and future development in the field of fibre-reinforced contact materials should thus be the development of low cost manufacturing processes. The first successes in this direction have already been attained. Using a metal/metal and a metal/non-metal fibre-reinforced material as examples, a manufacturing process will be described in the following which has already proven itself on a production scale and is distinguished above all by relatively low costs.

As an example for the metal matrix - metal fibre combination, the widely used AgNi material has been chosen. This contact material is used as a particle composite with nickel contents between 5 and 40 % to a large extent in switch instruments of low-voltage technology. Since silver and nickel are almost

completely immiscible in one another in the solid state, and molten silver dissolves only very little nickel as well, the AgNi material must be produced powder metallurgically till now. By extruding rough-pressed and sintered ingots, a marked anisotropy of the structure can be obtained. The alignment and forming of the nickel particles in the silver matrix is so great as a result, that a fibre-reinforced composite can already be spoken of with a certain justification. With the "short fibres" oriented perpendicular to the contact surface, contacts made of this material show, in addition to better mechanical and technological properties, an improved burnoff characteristic when compared to isotropically sintered contacts.

Still better properties are obtained through the use of continuous nickel fibres in the silver matrix. Also this material can be produced today in large amounts at favorable manufacturing costs. So-called clad wires whose cladding consists of silver and whose core consists of nickel are used as starting material. These clad wires are bundled and subjected to a strong non-cutting shaping process either discontinuously in a tube or continuously on a machine while enclosed by a slotted tube as shown schematically in figure 2. A prototype of such a system is already operating satisfactorily. Through the strong cold deformation and intermediate diffusion anneals, perfect bonding of the individual clad wires with one another and of the nickel fibres in the resulting silver matrix are obtained. As figure 3 shows the clad wires first orient themselves in an ideal manner and are then welded to one another so that no "grain boundaries" can be found any more in the silver matrix. [2]

AgNi fibre-reinforced composites are distinguished by very good mechanical and electrical properties, where the considerably greater ductility compared to isotropically sintered material should be emphasized first. Hardness, yield point, and tensile strength also show higher values than the corresponding sintered material. The contact properties are naturally of special interest. Mainly the low burnoff (material loss from melting and vaporization as a result of the spark during switching) of the fibre-reinforced material should be mentioned, this apparently being traceable to the good anchoring of the nickel fibres in the silver matrix. In a sintered composite the nickel particles are embedded in the silver matrix in a relatively finely dispersed way and are therefore easily ejected along with molten drops resulting from melting in the

arc. Figure 4 shows scanning electron microscope photos of the surface of a contact made of AgNi fibre-reinforced material after 100 switchings. The silver particles sputtered by the arc are deposited on the contact surface at the same distance around the contact spot.

As already mentioned previously, composites of silver with non-metallic components are applied above all where a low susceptibility to contact welding is required. The standard material for this area of application is the silver-graphite composite. Because of the immiscibility of the components, this material must be produced powder metallurgically. With a graphite content of about 5 %, the material is distinguished by fully preventing the contacts from welding together when switching on heavy currents. These excellent properties, however, are associated with the disadvantage of having very high burnoff when switching. If isotropic, sintered AgC is strongly deformed through extrusion, a distinct fibre structure results through which the properties can be considerably improved. If the "graphite fibres" are perpendicular to the contact surface, the material loss from burnoff amounts to about only 20 % of the material loss in the corresponding isotropically sintered material. Accordingly, the structure of the material is of decisive importance for the lifetime of the contact. [3]

For this reason attempts were made to further improve the properties of the material through the use of continuous graphite fibres in place of the stretched particles, this having led to various patent applications. Thus, for example, graphite whiskers or fibres are supposed to become aligned by exposing a silver melt to ultrasonic waves. Melt infiltration of a graphite fibre fleece was also proposed. These processes, however, are quite costly and for this reason have found no technical application to date.

On the other hand, the process already described for manufacturing AgNi fibre-reinforced materials can also be used in an appropriately modified form for the low cost production of composites with non-metallic "fibres". The manufacturing sequence is sketched in the following:

Tubes made of the matrix material, e.g. silver, are filled with powder of the desired second component, e.g. graphite, and shaped into so-called clad wires

by a non-cutting shaping process (hammer forging, rolling, drawing). This clad wire then consists of a silver cladding and a compacted graphite powder core. The wires are cut to length, bundled and subjected to strong cold forming while enclosed in a tube. During the process the silver claddings are cold welded and thus form the matrix of the fibre-reinforced material. The non-metallic component is then embedded in the matrix in a continuous, fibre-like manner with a very uniform distribution. Figure 5 shows transverse and longitudinal micrographs through a fiber-reinforced material AgC 95/5 produced using this process. The distribution of the fibres across the material cross section is almost ideal. The diameter of the graphite fibres amounts to about 60 μm in this state, but can still be reduced by further forming.

AgCdO commonly used as a particular composite can also be produced as a fibre-reinforced composite with the same process. A very uniform distribution of the CdO fibres over the sample cross section is also obtained here, which is not the case with powder metallurgical production or internal oxidation of the material. It has been found that the burnoff depends on the structure of the material to a great extent for AgCdO as well. If in place of pure silver a dispersion-hardened silver is used as the matrix, the burnoff of the fibre-reinforced composite can be reduced to half that of "normal" AgCdO produced by powder metallurgical process. This means doubling the lifetime of the contact.

The particle size and/or the fibre diameters can be varied within wide ranges. Approximately twice the particle diameter of the powder used can be taken as the smallest fibre diameter. Figure 6 shows the fracture pattern of an AgCdO fibre-reinforced composite with a fibre diameter of about 2 μm . It can be clearly seen that with this dimension the fibre diameter is of the size of the powder grains. If such a material is formed further e.g. by drawing or rolling, the silver matrix is pressed between the particles which are now lying one behind the other. Local interruptions arise as can be seen by the poorer distribution in the transverse microsection. With the usually desired fibre diameters of about 3 - 5 μm , this effect is not very pronounced, however. If the size of the powder grains is small compared to the desired fibre diameter, the strong, non-cutting shaping causes such a compaction of the powder that relatively stable rods or fibres of the powder material form in the silver matrix. These rods or fibres can be removed from the

matrix for examination using suitable etchants.

Figures 7 and 8 show a silver matrix with tin oxide fibres composite on which the matrix at the surface was partly removed by deep etching. The diameter of the SnO_2 fibres is about $60 \mu\text{m}$ in this stage. Commercially available SnO_2 with an unknown particle size was used to manufacture this material. With greater magnification, the pulled structure on the surface of the rods can be easily seen. Individual rods show slight cracks which can be traced to no heat treatment to sinter the powder having been carried out. The rods exist only in the pressed state. Through suitable heat treatments, however, sintering can be brought about in many cases.

It is obvious that using the process described here a multitude of material combinations can be produced. The following material combinations have already been tested in production:

AgCdO , AgSnO_2 , AgZnO , AgAl_2O_3 , AgMgO , AgC
and Ag Glass.

With the last mentioned material Ag Glass, linking of the powder particles can be brought about through suitable heat treatment after the non-cutting shaping, this resulting in relatively stable glass rods. It is recommended, however, to carry out this linking already during the shaping, e.g. by hot drawing, since in this way greater compaction of the glass is attained. Figures 9 show the deep-etched surface of an Ag Glass fibre-reinforced composite. The linking was carried out only after the non-cutting forming in this case.

Mainly high production cost stood in the way of large-scale application of fibre-reinforced composites not only in the area of contact technology. It can hardly be expected that the production processes can be simplified in the near future to the extent that the costs will become comparable to those of powder metallurgical processes. A comparison of only production costs, at least for noble metal contacts, is not meaningful. An economical consideration must therefore take additional factors into account and these will be discussed shortly in the following:

In business administration, the ratio of earnings to expenditures is what is understood by the term "profitability". When comparing two materials this concept cannot be applied in the classical meaning of business

administration. Therefore it will be replaced by the term "advantageousness". The advantageousness of a material compared to another material exists when the former results in fewer costs in a comparable application.

With noble metal-containing contact materials it is usual to divide the total price for a shaped piece (semi-finished product or finished contact piece) into

1. the so-called cost price for shaping K_F
- + 2. the noble metal value K_{EM}

Total cost GK

The cost price for forming is a value determined according to the principles of the firm's cost accounting, while on the other hand the noble metal value represents the product of the noble metal weight content and the officially posted market price for the noble metal. The latter value is influenced by a number of factors (above all political and economical) and for this reason is of late subject to large fluctuations.

For the user (e.g. switch device manufacturer), however, the total price (i.e. cost price for forming + noble metal value) is decisive, since this total price is included in the manufacturing costs of the product as a single cost. For this reason price comparisons are only meaningful when the total price is taken as a basis and simultaneously the different properties of the materials to be compared are also taken into account. Thus, with switching devices for example, the burnoff characteristic (material loss) of a contact material effects the lifetime of such a device quite essentially. This means that the thickness of the contact layer on a contact in such a device is determined essentially by the required lifetime (number of switchings) and the burnoff rate (material loss per switching).

If this aspect is taken into account, the following equation results for determining the advantageousness of using a contact material.

$$\text{Advantageousness} = \frac{\text{GK}_I \times \text{AF}_{II}}{\text{GK}_{II} \times \text{AF}_I}$$

with GK_I = total costs of material I
 AF_I = burnoff factor of material I

If the advantageousness $A > 1$, the new material II is more advantageous regarding cost compared to the previous material.

If the burnoff quotient Bq is defined as the ratio of the burnoff rates of the two materials, the following relation results:

$$A = \frac{(K_{EM} + K_F)_I}{(K_{EM} + K_F)_{II}} \quad . \quad Bq \text{ with } Bq = \frac{A F_I}{A F_{II}}$$

Example: Comparison of the materials AgNi 90/10 P (powder metallurgical) and AgNi 90/10 FRC (fibre-reinforced composite)

Assumption: Noble metal market price 222.20 DM/kg
1 kg contact material contains 900 g pure silver

$$K_{EM I} \text{ and } K_{EM II} = 200 \text{ DM}$$

The costs for forming amount to:

$$KF_I = 50 \text{ DM/kg (powder metallurgical)}$$

$$KF_{II} = 100 \text{ DM/kg (fibre-reinforced composite)}$$

With burnoff rates

$$AF_I = 1.0$$

$$AF_{II} = 0.5$$

$$Bq = \frac{1}{0.5} = 2$$

Result

$$A = \frac{200 + 50}{200 + 100} \quad . \quad 2 = 1.66$$

It is obvious that with an increasing noble metal market price, other conditions remaining the same, the advantageousness of material II increases. Thus with a noble metal market price of 444.40 DM/kg an advantageousness of $A = 1.8$ results. Similarly, the advantageousness increases with increasing burnoff quotient.

Summary:

A method for producing fibre-reinforced contact materials is described, being distinguished above all by its economy. Using an example it is shown that the use of fibre-reinforced composites can be economically more advantageous as compared to powder metallurgically

produced material in spite of higher forming costs.

Literature:

- [1] American Patent Nr. 2,295,338
- [2] D. Stöckel, Verbundwerkstoffe, DGM 1974
- [3] M. Poniatowski et al., 7. Int. Conf. El.
Contacts, Paris 1974

Sept. 8, 1942.

J. K. ELY

2,295,338

METHOD OF MAKING ELECTRICAL CONTACT MEMBERS
Original Filed April 15, 1940

Fig. 1 American Patent of 1942

Fig. 2 Continuous Production of Fiber-Reinforced Metals

Fig. 3 Cross-section of a Ag/Steel-Composite during Production

Fig. 4 Surface of Ag/Ni - Composite after 100 Switchings

Fig. 5 Ag/C - Fibre Composite

Fig. 6 Fracture of a Ag/CdO - Fibre Composite

Fig. 7 Ag/SnO₂ - Fibre Composite (Ag-Matrix partly removed by deep etching)

Fig. 8 Ag/SnO₂ - Fibre Composite (Ag-Matrix partly removed by deep etching)

Fig. 9 Ag/Glass-Fibre Composite

Fig. 10 Ag/Glass-Fibre Composite